

INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS AS MEANS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' MENTAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The article presents interactive methods of teaching English. The author describes the possibility of using some of these methods and techniques in teaching English as a foreign language., traditional reproductive education, the passive subordinate role of the student, cannot solve such problems. To solve them, new pedagogical technologies, effective forms of organization of the educational process, active teaching methods are required. The main idea in this case is the idea of an active personality, aimed primarily at their own development through interaction with the outside world. Namely, the development of mental activity of students as one of the components of the activity of the individual as a whole.

INTRODUCTION

Rapidly developing changes in society and the economy today require a person to be able to quickly adapt to new conditions, find optimal solutions to complex issues, showing flexibility and creativity, and not get lost in a situation of uncertainty. The task of education is to prepare a graduate who has the necessary set of modern knowledge, skills and qualities that allow him to feel confident in an independent life. Alas, traditional reproductive education, the passive subordinate role of the student, cannot solve such problems. Currently, the state educational standard has high requirements for students. Short terms of mastering topics, a large amount of information are modern conditions for the general educational process. In order to fulfill such requests, a new method of teaching must be found. Due to this, in the methodology of teaching English, there has been a transition from a communicative approach to an interactive one. The interactive approach is one of the varieties of the communicative approach.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Interactive ("Inter" - mutual and "act" - act) - means the ability to interact, be in a conversation, dialogue with someone. Those. Interactive learning is interactive learning, during which the teacher interacts with students. [3, p.112].

In the psychological and pedagogical literature, the concept of "activity" is considered as "cognitive activity", "intellectual activity", "mental activity". G.I. Shchukina's cognitive activity

is characterized as "the integration of a search orientation in learning, cognitive interest and its satisfaction with the help of various sources of knowledge, favorable conditions for the implementation of activities" [7, p.80]. I.F. Kharlamov understands cognitive activity as "an active state of the child, which is characterized by the desire for learning, mental stress and the manifestation of volitional efforts in the process of mastering knowledge" [5, p.31]. The position of T.I. Shamova, who considers cognitive activity as "a quality of a person, manifested in relation to the content and process of activity, in the desire for effective mastery of knowledge and methods of obtaining it, in the mobilization of volitional efforts in achieving the goal of learning" [6, p.37].

In the studies of I.S. Yakiman's cognitive activity is identified with mental activity, and is determined by the "personal, biased attitude of the child to the acquired knowledge" [8, p.71]. D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya uses the term "intellectual activity" and considers it as "continuation of mental activity outside the situational setting, not due to practical needs or external subjective negative assessment of the work" [1, p.122].

The purpose of interactive learning is that all participants in the lesson are in interaction. They are all actively involved in the learning process. The teacher acts as an assistant. In the course of interactive communication, students learn to think, solve problems, make decisions and participate in discussions. Modern pedagogy has many interactive methods. Among them are the following:

- Creative tasks;
- Educational games (role-playing games, educational games, etc.);
- Work in small groups, pairs, triplets (reception "2.4, together");
- "Carousel" method;
- "Aquarium";
- "Brainstorming" or another name "brainstorming";
- "Openworksaw";
- "Brownianmotion"
- Drawing up a mental map;_

This list can be replenished, because each teacher can implement their own techniques and methods. The scope of one article does not make it possible to describe all the interactive methods of teaching English, so we will consider only those that are used in practice. Reception of drawing up a "Mental Map" (Mind Map). For the first time, the term was proposed by the British psychologist, the author of the memorization technique, Tony Buzan. A map is a diagram that visually demonstrates various ideas, tasks, theses related to each other and united by some common problem. The map allows you to cover the whole situation as a whole, as well as to keep a large amount of information in mind at the same time. Graphically, this map can be drawn in the form of the sun (in the center of which the main concept is indicated) from which the rays of association depart. For example, "mental map" for phrasal verbs.

A verb is written in the center (to look - look) from which the prepositions with which it is used depart with rays (to look for - look; to look after - take care; to look on - count, etc.).

Another example of such a map is the "Fishbone" method. We are offered a fish skeleton. In the "head" we highlight the main problem, on the upper bones, students identify the cause of the problem, and on the lower bones, facts are written that reflect the essence of the problem.

Select position method. The students are given a problematic question, where they should be divided into 3 groups. The first group has a point of view "For", the second "Against", and the third "I don't know, I haven't defined my own position". Students are divided into groups and discuss the correctness of their position. One or more members of each group argue their position, after which a collective discussion of the problem takes place and the correct decision is made. For example, discussing such a problem as "The Internet". Initially, the teacher provides students with the phrase: Just a century ago we didn't even know about computers and the Internet. But today we take them for granted and can't imagine our life without these inventions, especially without internet... After that, the topic is discussed in groups.

The most interesting method used in practice is the Sinkwain method. Cinquain - (from French cinquains, English cinquain) - a five-line poetic form that arose in the United States at the beginning of the 20th century under the influence of Japanese poetry. Later it began to be used for didactic purposes, as an effective method for the development of figurative speech, which allows you to quickly get the result [1, p.105].

1. The first line is the designation of the topic using one word (noun);
2. Description of the topic (2 adjectives);
3. Description of the action, according to the proposed topic (3 verbs);
4. Drawing up a phrase of 4 words that expresses the attitude to the topic (different parts of speech);
5. Selection of a synonym for the topic (1 word).

This method was first carried out by us with students of the 7th grade. The topic we were studying at that moment was "Journey". The work plan was as follows:

1. At the beginning of the lesson, the teacher should introduce the students to the syncwain method and explain the rules of writing.
2. Then 5-10 minutes are given for the students to compose and exchange their options.
3. After that, the syncwines are read and the most suitable options are selected.

Here are some examples of work:

1. Travelling
2. Exciting, useful
3. Togo, tofly, toswim
4. Thebestwaytorelax__
5. My dream

I would like to note that interactivity will be more effective if multimedia technology is applied in practice. Interactive methods also include presentations using various aids. In conclusion, it should be noted that the interactive teaching method increases motivation in learning English, the learning process becomes more interesting and exciting, and students

feel freer. In addition, all methods and techniques develop communication skills, teach to work in a team and listen to each other.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A comparative analysis of various interpretations of personality activity shows that the concepts of "intellectual activity", "cognitive activity" and "mental activity" can be considered synonymous. We define mental activity as the desire for the most complete knowledge of objects and phenomena of the surrounding world. Mental activity is considered as a set of mental actions or mental operations: analysis, synthesis, comparison, abstraction, generalization, classification, systematization. Mental activity is caused by a cognitive need, accompanied by a special emotional state and manifested in the mobilization of volitional efforts. Thus, the following definition of mental activity follows from the above: mental activity is a quality of a person, manifested in the desire for knowledge of objects and phenomena of the surrounding world, which is caused by a cognitive need and is accompanied by a special emotional state and manifestation of volitional efforts.

For the development of mental activity of students, there is a real need to use non-traditional models, technologies and methods of creative work with students and choose the most effective and rational ones. Among the learning models are passive, active and interactive [8]. All of them pursue a common goal - the assimilation of knowledge by students. The features of the passive model are that students learn material from the words of the teacher or from the text of the textbook, do not communicate with each other and do not perform creative tasks. Active methods involve stimulating cognitive activity and independence of students through communication in the "student-teacher" system, the presence of creative homework. Interactive learning implies a different logic of the educational process from the usual one: the experience and knowledge of the participants serve as a source of their mutual learning. The interactive process is characterized by high intensity of communication, change and variety of activities, purposeful reflection. S.S. Kashlev defines an interactive learning model as a purposeful enhanced inter-subject interaction between a teacher and students to create optimal conditions for their development [2, p. 116]. It should be emphasized that the principle of interactivity can be traced in most modern educational technologies, which are based on a student-centered approach. This approach provides for various forms of work that encourage the student to work independently at the level of their physical, intellectual, emotional capabilities and thereby activates the mental activity of students [3, 282]. The activation of the cognitive activity of students in the classroom is a general didactic problem that is fully inherent in the features of the subject "foreign language". Given the specifics of this subject, interactive methods of teaching can provide the necessary conditions for the activation of the mental and speech activity of each student, providing him with the opportunity to understand, comprehend new language material, get sufficient speech practice to form the necessary skills and abilities. It is advisable to start creating an atmosphere of foreign language communication with proverbs, sayings, quotes, commenting on or discussing which, students get the opportunity to analyze their knowledge on the topic studied, to get an additional incentive to formulate their own motives. When studying country-specific material, tables with information gaps can be used. Students

are divided into pairs/groups. Each student receives a certain piece of information about the same object/fact and the problematic task is to give complete, exhaustive information about it. Thus, communicating with each other, students develop the skills of asking questions, building sentences, and synthesizing new knowledge on a particular topic.

Role-playing simulation gives students the opportunity to understand and study educational material from different perspectives, feeling themselves in a certain role. This technique motivates speech activity, because students find themselves in a situation where the need to say something, ask, find out, argue is actualized, abstracting from the educational process. One of the interactive techniques is the method of projects. In the process of independent and group work on the project, they develop a culture of communication, the ability to briefly and easily formulate thoughts, tolerantly treat the opinion of communication partners; the ability to extract and process information, including with the help of modern computer technologies, to present the result of collective creativity. Working with texts using the Mosaic method allows students to obtain a large amount of information in a short time. This method initiates interest, encourages questions, enables students to take an active part in the learning process and share their knowledge with each other. Each student (subgroup) reads a short text, then looks for a partner who has read another text. After discussing their texts, making the necessary notes, students change partners. Each student masters all the texts and, systematizing them, gets a general picture of the situation, the problem. When working with an audio text, after monitoring the perception and understanding of foreign speech by ear, it is advisable to conduct problematic discussions. This is a special form of collective cooperation that causes active intense mental activity [4, p. 112].

CONCLUSION

At the final stage of studying the topic, you can use an essay. Such creative written work (both individual and group) encourages students to describe their personal experience, to argue their point of view on the topic, problem. When systematizing, repeating the material, it is possible to use the "Memory Card" as a simple method of fixing thoughts, ideas, discussions. Quickly, according to the principle of associations, ideas on the topic are proposed, all of them are recorded. In the lesson, students create a mind map as a collaborative product. At home, they design it as an individual product, showing their language abilities and creativity. In the future, memory cards are used as reference notes in the organization of various types of speech activity of students. High school students successfully systematize the studied material in the form of a cluster, which allows not only to cover more information than can be obtained during normal work, but also to establish causal relationships between the "clusters". At the stage of reflection, the "Complete the phrase" technique is effective. To identify the effectiveness of the training session (mastering the material on the topic), students are invited to complete a number of incomplete phrases regarding the content, atmosphere, and organization of interaction. Thus, students show their personal attitude to the learned material. Methods of interactive technologies are focused on the independent activity of students - individual, pair, group. Students interact with each other and with the teacher, whose role changes from a controller to an equal partner and consultant. He becomes the organizer of independent work of students, using a variety of forms and methods of

educational activities that allow revealing the subjective experience of the student, encourages students to express themselves in a foreign language, use various methods of completing tasks without fear of making a mistake, giving the wrong answer. The teacher helps students to choose the most significant and interesting types and forms of work for them, encourages the desire of everyone to find their own way of solving the problem, analyze the work of classmates during the lesson, choose and master the most rational ways, allowing each student to show initiative, independence, creating an environment for natural self-expression in a foreign language, giving the opportunity to realize oneself in cognition, learning activities, behavior, communication.

Thus, the teacher activates the activity of each student, creates situations for the development of their mental activity in the learning process.

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